

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№4

2026

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Elektron nashr. 2026-yil, aprel.

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoirazimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Faxridinov Zafarjon Faxridin o'g'li, O'zb. Res. Bosh prokuraturasi HIJQKD boshqarma boshlig'i
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Anijon viloyati prokurorining o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zb. Res. Bosh prokuraturasi IJQK Departamentining Namangan viloyati boshqarmasi boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.
Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamxonovna, bank-moliya akademiyasi professori, DSc., professor.
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Okil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjayevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Fakhriddinov Zafarjon Fakhriddin ogli, Head of the DCEC under the Prosecutor General's Office of the Rep. of Uzb.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Prosecutor of Anijan Region
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of the Namangan Regional Department of the Department of Internal Affairs of Rep. of Uzb.
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamkhanovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Geografiya fanlari doktori, professori
Umirzoqov Ja'sur Artiqboy o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Zebo Kuldasheva, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Professor
Umirzokov Jasur Artiqboy ugli, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor
Zebo Kuldasheva, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

O'ZBEKISTONDA RAQAMLI TO'LOV INFRATUZILMASINI SHAKILLANISHI VA RIVOJLANISH DINAMIKASI: TARIXIY, ILMIY HAMDA BOZOR TAHLILI	32
A.A. Akbarov, X.R. Aliyev	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINI TASHKIL ETISHNING ME'YORIY-HUQUQIY ASOSLARI VA ULARNING IQTISODIY AHAMIYATI.....	42
Karayev Payzillaxon Yusufxonovich	
TURIZM KORXONALARINING INNOVATSION FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA MOLIYAVIY AKTIVLARINING ROLI.....	47
Ruzibayeva Nargiza Xakimovna	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA EKOLOGIK SOLIQLAR VA TO'LOVLAR TIZIMI TAHLILI	53
Sadullayev Rasulbek Palvanbayevich, Abdolnizozov Murodbek Madiyarovich	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA IJTIMOYIY HIMOYA TIZIMINI MOLIYALASHTIRISHDA AMALGA OSHIRILAYOTGAN ISHLAR VA TIZIMGA KIRITILAYOTGAN O'ZGARISHLAR.....	59
Kasimova Gulyar Axmatovna, Aripova Kamola Botir qizi	
MINTAQAVIY RIVOJLANISHNI KOMPLEKS BAHOLASH VA PROGNOZLASHDA EKONOMETRIK VA SUN'IY INTELLEKT USULLARINING INTEGRATSIYASI	64
Namazov Gafur Shokulovich	
BALIQCILIK SUBYEKTLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA DUNYO MAMLAKATLARINING O'RNI	69
Beglayev Uchqun Xurramovich	
KAMBAG'ALLIK FENOMENINING IJTIMOYIY-IQTISODIY VA NAZARIY-KONTSEPTUAL ASOSLARI	75
Musulmonova Shahlo Nasriddinovna	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA HISOB VA BIZNES JARAYONLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING ZAMONAVIY YO'NALISHLARI	81
Artikova R.A.	
AKSIYADORLIK JAMIYATLARIDA DIVIDEND TO'LASH QOBILİYATI KOEFFITSIYENTINING MAQBUL ORALIG'INI ANIQLASH VA UNING INVESTITSION SAMARADORLIKKA TA'SIRI.....	88
Ibragimov G'anjion G'ayratovich	
STRATEGIES TO RAISE AWARENESS OF NATURAL POLLUTION AMIDST RISING POPULATION DENSITY AND GDP PER CAPITA IN UZBEKISTAN	93
Axliddin Aroplitdinovich Valiyev, Askarov Farhod Rakhmatovich	
РОЛЬ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА В ESG-ОРИЕНТИРОВАННОМ РАЗВИТИИ ВЫСШИХ УЧЕБНЫХ ЗАВЕДЕНИЙ.....	99
Айматова Фарида Хуразовна	
KORXONALARDA INVESTITSION FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANISHINING ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	107
Shukurillaev Jahongir Botir o'g'li	
DEHQON XO'JALIKLARINI MOLIYAVIY QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASHDA KREDITLAR MIQDORINI DIFFERENSIYALLASHTIRISH: NAZARIY VA AMALIY YONDASHUVLAR	113
Xakimov Zafar Ibragimovich	
KICHIK BIZNESNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING IQTISODIY MEXANIZMLARI	118
Tadjimirzayev Anvar Abduvoxidovich, Batirova Raxima Abdujabborovna	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA HUDUDIY MARKETING STRATEGIYALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	124
Muhammadiyeva Nodira	
SUN'IY INTELLEKT DAVRIDA HUDUDIY RIVOJLANISHNI STATISTIK HISOBLASH METODOLOGIYASINI QAYTA BAHOLASH MEZONLARI (SCOPUS VA WEB OF SCIENCE DA INDEKSLANGAN ILMIY NASHRLAR TAHLILI ASOSIDA).....	131
Santjar Abdumurodovich Sattorov	
QORAQALPOG'ISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING HUDUDIY-IQTISODIY OMILLARI VA ISTIQBOLLARI	139
Allamuratova Perida Maxsetbaevna	

XORAZM VILOYATIDA AHOLI BANDLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIKNING ROLI VA AHAMIYATI	144
Ro'zmatova Farahongiz Bekmurotovna, Yarmetova Nargiza Shiximbayevna	
MAHALLIY VA XALQARO TURIZM BOZORIDA RAQOBATBARDOSHLIKNI SHAKLLANTIRISH OMILLARI, TAMOIYILLARI VA MEKANIZMLARI	152
Alikulov Samar Abdurashidovich	
TRANSPORT XIZMATLARINING SOHALAR BO'YICHA TAQSIMOTI VA SAMARADORLIK KO'RSATKICHLARI TASNIFI	159
Karimova Shaxnoza Uktamovna	
RAQAMLI TO'LOVLAR VA O'ZBEKISTONDA KORPORATIV BOSHQARUV SHAFFOFLIGI	165
Ruziyeva Barno Yadgarovna	
ESG-ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ НА ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ ПО ПРОИЗВОДСТВУ ПОЛИМЕРНОЙ УПАКОВКИ: ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ И МИРОВЫЕ ПРАКТИКИ.....	172
Ташпулатов Дильмурад Рустамович	
MAJBURIY IJRO HARAKATLARINI RAQAMLASHTIRISHNI YANADA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	177
Matmuratova Nasiba Azatovna	
OZIQ-OVQAT KORXONALARIDA KICHIK BIZNESNING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI CHEKLOVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI	181
Pulatov Abdulla	
INVESTITSION LOYIHALARNING IQTISODIYOTDA TUTGAN O'RNI VA ULARNI MOLIYALASHTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	185
Nazarov Aziz Avazovich	
ФИНАНСОВАЯ УСТОЙЧИВОСТЬ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯ: ПРОБЛЕМЫ И РЕШЕНИЯ.....	190
Тажибаева Кызларгул Ажиниязовна	
IQTISODIYOTNI MODERNIZATSIYALASH SHAROITIDA O'ZBEKISTONDA SANOAT KORXONALARI FAOLIYATINI DIVERSIFIKATSIYALASHNING MAQSADLI PROGNOZ PARAMETRLARI.....	197
Omonova Nafisa Qahramon qizi	
MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES IN WOMEN'S BUSINESS: GENDER-SPECIFIC APPROACHES, INNOVATIVE MODELS, AND DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION.....	200
Ahrorova Asila	
TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATI KORXONALARI INNOVATSION FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGIGA TA'SIR QILUVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI	207
Hakimova Oydina Abdulhamidovna, Yuldasheva Nilufar Abduvaxidovna	
INSON TARAQQIYOTI INDEKSI VA UNI ANIQLAB BERUVCHI KO'RSATKICHLARNING KORRELYATSION-REGRESSION TAHLILI.....	212
Tursunov Rasul Tairovich	
ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ БУХГАЛТЕРСКОГО УЧЕТА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ В УСЛОВИЯХ ПЕРЕХОДА НА МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЕ СТАНДАРТЫ ФИНАНСОВОЙ ОТЧЕТНОСТИ.....	218
Эргашева Феруза Насруллаевна	
ENHANCING THE METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK FOR THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM VILLAGES IN UZBEKISTAN	226
Khudaynazarova Dilorom Khayrullaevna	
THE ROLE OF INNOVATION IN ENSURING COMPETITIVENESS IN THE GREEN ECONOMY	231
Musadjanova Nargiza Abduvoxid qizi	
O'ZBEKISTONDA TURIZM SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA INGLIZ TILINING O'RNI VA SAMARADORLIGI.....	238
Saodat Sadriddinova	
OLIY TA'LIMDA CHET TILLARNI O'QITISH UCHUN RAQAMLI BOSHQARUV STRATEGIYALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	243
Saida Xabibullayeva	
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ФИСКАЛЬНЫХ МЕХАНИЗМОВ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО РЕГУЛИРОВАНИЯ В СФЕРЕ ТУРИЗМА РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН.....	247
Исматиллаева Роза Тухтамуратовна, Тураева Сурия Тельмановна	

INNOVATSION IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA PAXTA-TO'QIMACHILIK KLASTERINING QIYMAT YARATISH UZLUKSIZ ZANJIRIDA AGROSERVIS XIZMATLARI KO'RSATISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	252
Kudratova Iroda Turdibayevna	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI IQTISODIYOTIDA DIVERSIFIKATSIYANING AHAMIYATI	257
Nurullayeva Raushan Koptleuovna, Nurimbetov Timur Uzaqbergenovich	
FIZIKA UMUMIY KURSIGA NANOTEXNOLOGIYA TUSHUNCHALARINI KIRITISHNING METODIK ASPEKTLARI VA KOMPONENTLARI	260
Sottarov Abduvali Umirqulovich	
BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH SHAROITIDA EKOLOGIK HISOBOTLAR VA ULARNING TUTGAN O'RNI.....	266
Sayfullayev Mexroj Sayfullayevich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA EKOLOGIK LOYIHALARNI MOLİYALASHTIRISH MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	272
Rahmanova Sitara Bahodir qizi	
SANOAT KORXONALARIDA OPERATSION MENEJMENT SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	277
Satvoldiyev Ulugbek Kamilovich	
IQTISODIY O'SISH DRAYVERLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA SUN'IY INTELLEKT TEXNOLOGIYALARI ASOSIDA MOLİYAVIY XAVFLARNI BOSHQARISH.....	283
Turopova Nigora Xolmurod qizi	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA INNOVATSION INVESTITSİYALASH VA MUQOBIL MOLİYALASHTIRISH MEXANIZMLARINI JORIY ETISH (SIRDARYO VILOYATI MISOLIDA)	286
Maxamadiyev Turg'unboy Jumabayevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA XO'JALIK JAMIYATLARI KUZATUV KENGASHLARI FAOLIYATINING ILMIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH.....	292
Valijonov Akmaljon	
IQTISODIYOTNING AGRAR SEKTORIDA INNOVATSION FAOLIYATNI BOSHQARISH: NAZARIY VA USLUBIY YONDASHUVLAR	296
Matrasulov Baxodir Erbutayevich	
O'ZBEKISTON MOLİYA TIZIMIDA MAHALLIY MOLİYANING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI.....	303
Safarmurodova Marjona To'raqulovna	
МЕТОД ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОГО ТУРИСТИЧЕСКОГО ПАКЕТА	308
Наурызбаев Алиакбар Рустамович	
QASHQADARYO VILOYATI SANOATINI XUDUDIY TARKIBINI TAKOMILASHTIRISH YO'LLARI	311
Uralov Eliboy Omonovich	
INNOVATSION VA AN'ANAVIY YONDASHUVLAR ASOSIDA KO'CHAT YETISHTIRISHNING TAQQOSLAMA TAHLILI	316
Abdulfarmonov Farrux Faxriddinovich	
EKSPORT IMKONIYATLARI VA LOGISTIKA SAMARADORLIGINI SOLISHTIRISH.....	320
Safarova Muxabbat Radjabovna	
IJORAT BANKLARIDA KREDIT PORTFELI O'SISHI DINAMIKASI VA LIKVIDLIK KO'RSATKICHLARI O'RTASIDAGI BOG'LIQLIK	324
Sulaymanov Samandarboy Adhambek o'g'li	
KO'CHMAS MULKNI OMMAVIY BAHOLASHNING INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARI.....	331
Xushvaqtov Jasur Shuhrat o'g'li	
TURIZM XIZMATLARINI KO'RSATUVCHI SUBYEKTLARDA MOLİYAVIY HISOBOTLARNI MHXS GA O'TKAZISHDA TRANSFORMATSIYA REJASINI ISHLAB CHIQUISH MASALALARI.....	339
G'afforov Ilhomjon Ilyosjonovich	
QURILISH SANOATI KORXONALARI DIVERSIFIKATSIYALASHUVINING IQTISODIY MEXANIZMLARI	343
Yembergenova Aynur Aydosbaevna	
KAMBAG'ALLIKNI QISQARTIRISHDA AYOLLAR TADBIRKORLIGINI RIVOJLANISHNING NAZARIY JIHATLARI	351
Ulashova Zarnigor Botirali qizi	

KAPITAL BOZORI ORQALI MAMLAKAT IQTISODIYOTIGA INVESTITSIYA JALB QILISHNING BELARUS TAJRIBASI	357
Abduraxmanov Adham Raxmatullayevich	
BARQAROR QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI AMALIYOTLARINI JORIY ETISHDA XULQ-ATVOR OMILLARINING NAZARIY VA AMALIY AHAMIYATI	362
Tadjiyev Abdusame Abduhamidovich	
SANOAT KORXONALARIDA RISKLARNI BOSHQARISH TIZIMINI JORIY ETISHNING ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLARI	367
Abduxamid Abdumalikovich Bektemirov	
O'ZBEKISTONDA MEHMONXONALARNI MOLIYALASHTIRISH ORQALI JOYLASHTIRISH TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	373
Xasanova Naimaxon Akmal qizi	
SOLIQ YUKINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISHNING XORIJIY MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBASI	381
Jovliyeva Zuhra Chori qizi	
SANOATNI BARQAROR RIVOJLANTIRISHDA "YASHIL" INVESTITSİYALARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISHNING IQTISODIY MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	386
Ibragimov Zaxid Taxirovich	
ЗАРУБЕЖНЫЙ ОПЫТ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ БАНКОВСКИМИ АКТИВАМИ И ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ЕГО ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ В ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫЙ БАНК РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН	395
Т.И.Бобакулов, Тухтамышева Гулнора Усмановна	
AGRAR TARMOQQA JALB QILINAYOTGAN INVESTITSİYALAR SAMARADORLIGINI ISHLAB CHIQRISH FUNKSIYALARI YORDAMIDA EKONOMETRIK BAHOLASH.....	401
Xatamov Ochildi Qurbonovich, Badalov Jamshid Jamolovich	
IJARA OPERATSIYALARIDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINING KAMCHILIKLARI VA UZVIY TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	409
Oripova Saodat Mirfotix qizi	
SANOAT KORXONALARINING INVESTITSION SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISH.....	414
Xolboyeva farangiz xayrulloevna	
SUN'IY INTELEKT VA RAQAMLI VOSITALARNING TA'LIM JARAYONIDAGI O'RNI.....	419
To'xtamisheva Dilrabo Shermonovna	
MEVA-SABZAVOT MAHSULOTLARI EKSPORTINI KENGAYTIRISHNING IQTISODIY MEKANIZMLARI	424
Kalenov K.T.	
HUNARMANDCHILIK BRENDLARINING BOZOR OMILLAR TIZIMINI (MAHSULOT, NARX, TAQSIMOT, TARG'IBOT) TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING USLUBIY ASOSLARI	428
Ergasheva Aziza	
NAMANGAN VILOYATI IQTISODIYOTIDA TARKIBIY O'ZGARISHLAR: HUDUDIY VA TARMOQ TAHLILI	436
Tohirov Jahongir Muzaffar o'g'li	
WATER HARVESTING FOR CLIMATE RESILIENCE IN UZBEKISTAN'S AGRICULTURE: OPPORTUNITIES, BARRIERS, AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS	445
Kripa Mondal, Dr. Anita Banerjee	
O'ZBEKISTONDA TABIIY VA IQTISODIY RESURSLARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH ORQALI HUDUDIY IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHNI TA'MINLASH YO'LLARI	454
Sattarov Abdusamat Umirqulovich	
TO'QIMACHILIK KORXONALARIDA INNOVATSION FAOLIYATNI BOSHQARISH SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH VA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI	459
Nasibboyev Fazliddin Sirojiddinovich	
O'ZBEKISTON TIJORAT BANKLARIDA RISKLARNI MONITORING QILISH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDAGI MAVJUD MUAMMOLAR VA ULARNI BARTARAF QILISH YO'LLARI	464
Hamroyev Sherzod Axtamovich	
SIRKULYAR IQTISODIYOT — IQTISODIY BARQARORLIKNING MUHIM OMILI	471
Hasanov Sh. Sh.	

МАРКЕТИНГОВЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ КАК ИНСТРУМЕНТ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ ВУЗА.....	482
<i>Алиев Абдулазиз Исмаилович, Кахрамонова Азиза Шухрат кизи</i>	
TEMIR YO'L SOHASINING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	488
<i>Orifova Ximoyat Shovkat qizi</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA ZIYORAT TURIZMINI TASHKIL ETISH VA RIVOJLANTIRISHDA XALQARO TAJRIBADAN FOYDALANISH YO'LLARI.....	494
<i>Raximova Dilfuza Mirzakasimovna</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA MILLIY HUNARMANDCHILIKNING IQTISODIY SALOHIYATINI BAHOLASH VA EKONOMETRIK PROGNOZLASH	503
<i>Xushnazarova Maxzuna Gulamdjanovna</i>	
MINTAQAVIY IQTISODIY O'SISHNI BAHOLASHDA EKONOMETRIK MODELLAR VA GEOSTATISTIK USULLARNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH: SURXONDARYO VILOYATI MISOLIDA	509
<i>Sattorov Sanjar Abdumurodovich</i>	
XODIMLARNI MOTIVATSIYA QILISH VA ULARNING ISH FAOLIYATIGA TA'SIRI: O'ZBEKISTONDAGI KICHIK VA O'RTA BIZNES MISOLIDA	518
<i>Yuldashov Aziz</i>	
RAQOBAT MUHITIDA AVTOMOBIL SANOATI KORXONALARIDA BRENND STRATEGIYASINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MEKANIZMLARI	522
<i>Boboyev L. Kadrxo'ja Djuraxodjeyevich</i>	
XODIMLARNI O'QITISH, QAYTA TAYYORLASH VA ISHSIZLARNI KASBGA YO'NALTIRISHNING XORIJ TAJRIBASI (GERMANIYA MISOLIDA).....	528
<i>Sattorov Ramziddin Shovxiddin o'g'li</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON TIJORAT BANKLARI MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINING HOZIRGI HOLATI TAHLILI.....	533
<i>Yangiboyev Sardor Ernazar o'g'li</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON HUDUDLARIDA SANOAT ISHLAB CHIQRISHINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA CHIQUINDISIZ VA AYLANMA IQTISODIYOT TAMOYILLARINI QO'LLASHNING ASOSIY YO'NALISHLARI.....	542
<i>Nabiyeva Nilufar Olim qizi</i>	
МАШИННОЕ ОБУЧЕНИЕ В ПРОГНОЗИРОВАНИИ РЫНОЧНЫХ ТЕНДЕНЦИЙ В УСЛОВИЯХ ПЕРЕХОДА К ЗЕЛЁНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ	548
<i>Тен Марина Владимировна</i>	
РОЛЬ, СУЩНОСТЬ И ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО МЕДИЦИНСКОГО СТРАХОВАНИЯ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН.....	555
<i>Каюмова Гузел Иброхимхановна</i>	
QURILISH KORXONALARIDA AKTIVLARNI TAN OLIISHNING XALQARO STANDARTLARGA MOSLASHTIRISHNI O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI	562
<i>Yahyojev To'liqin Ismatulla o'g'li</i>	
IQTISODIYOTNI RAQAMLASHTIRISH SHAROITIDA MEVA-SABZAVOTCHILIK KORXONALARINI BOSHQARUV MEKANIZMLARI	566
<i>Xudoyberganova Dilnoza Anvarjon qizi</i>	
QURILISH KORXONALARIDA BOSHQARUV MUNOSABATLARI MAZMUNI VA ULARNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	572
<i>Toshimov Azizbek Hakimovich</i>	
RIVOJLANGAN MAMLAKATLARDAGI KOMPANIYALAR KAPITALINI MAKSIMALLASHTIRISHNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI	576
<i>Muradova Dildora Abdusalimovna</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON TIJORAT BANKLARDAGI KREDIT RISKLARINI BOSHQARISHDA BAZEL III TALABLARI	581
<i>Norova Nozima Nabiyevna</i>	
ЦИРКУЛЯРНАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА КАК ИНСТРУМЕНТ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ: ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ, МИРОВАЯ ПРАКТИКА И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ВНЕДРЕНИЯ	588
<i>Алиева С.С.</i>	

KORXONALARDA SOLIQ HISOBINI TASHKIL ETISH VA UNING BUXGALTERIYA HISOBİ BILAN O'ZARO BOG'LIQLIGI	594
Mamadiyarov Dilshad Uralovich, Normurodov Sarvar Norboy o'g'li	
HUDUDIY KORXONALARDA BIZNES JARAYONLARNI BARQAROR RIVOJLANTIRISHDA ZAMONAVIY BOSHQARUV MODEL VA TAMOYILLARINING AHAMIYATI	599
Azimova Maxfuza Rashidovna	
ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИЯ СЕЛЬСКОГО ХОЗЯЙСТВА - ВАЖНЫЙ ФАКТОР ПОВЫШЕНИЯ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ СЕЛЬСКОГО ХОЗЯЙСТВА	604
Пирназаров Шоназар Махтовович	
RAQAMLASHTIRISH JARAYONINING O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIRI.....	608
Saydullayev Azamat Jo'raqul o'g'li, Abdinazarov Suhrobbek Bekmurod o'g'li	
SINGAPUR VA JANUBIY KOREYADA BIZNES SUBYEKTLARINI DAVLAT TOMONIDAN QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH.....	615
Nasriddinov Qobilbek Qurbonbekovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL ENERGIYAGA O'TISHNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI	620
Hayitov Jamshid Xolboyevich	
LOYIHALARNI STRATEGIK REJALASHTIRISHDA BIG DATA TEXNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH MEKANIZMLARI	625
Xamrayev Zuxritdin Abduraxmanovich	
LOYIHA SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA LOYIHA JAMOASINING ROLI VA FUNKSIYALARI	629
Utemuratov Sadik Muratovich	
IQLIM O'ZGARISHI VA RESURLAR CHEKLANGANLIGI SHAROITIDA YASHIL TURIZM MODELLARINING NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLARINI TIZIMLI TAHLIL QILISH VA RIVOJLANTIRISH	633
Rasulova Nigora Yusupovna	
ВЛИЯНИЕ КУЛЬТУРНЫХ РАЗЛИЧИЙ НА ПРОЦЕСС УПРАВЛЕНЧЕСКОЙ КОММУНИКАЦИИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ: СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ ПОДХОД.....	637
Латипов Ашур Али Рустам угли, Хамидов Далер Дилшодович	
ADAM SMIT IQTISODIY G'OYALARI VA ULARNING ZAMONAVIY IQTISODIYOTDAGI AHAMIYATI.....	641
Boymatov Xoliyor Qurbonovich	
SANOAT KORXONALARIDA MAHSULOT SIFATINI BOSHQARISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNING O'RNI	646
Baytanov O'ralboy Miraqul o'g'li	
SOCIAL PROTECTION SYSTEM OF THE POPULATION IN THE CONDITIONS OF A TRANSFORMATIONAL ECONOMY.....	651
M. Sh. Rakhimova	
SANOATNI YASHIL TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA RIVOJLANTIRISH: XORIJIY TAJRIBA, SIYOSIY MEKANIZMLAR VA O'ZBEKISTON UCHUN AMALIY XULOSALAR	655
To'qumbetov Og'abek Shavkat o'g'li, Ruziyeva Dilobar Isomjonovna	
TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA AHOLI FAROVONLIGINING O'RNI VA AHAMIYATI	661
Bobayev Isroiljon Abdinabiyevich	
IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE MAHALLA INSTITUTION IN THE TERRITORIAL GOVERNANCE SYSTEM: MODERNIZATION OF INSTITUTIONAL AND ORGANIZATIONAL MECHANISMS	666
Mirbabayev Farrukh Atkhamovich	
AHOLINI UY-JOY BILAN TA'MINLASHDA DAVLAT BUDJETI XARAJATLARI TAHLILI	674
Xannarov Komiljon Karimovich	
INVESTITSIYA KO'CHMAS MULKI HISOBINI TASHKIL QILISH VA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	681
Maxmudov Jamshed Ashrafovich	
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МЕХАНИЗМА ЦИФРОВОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ РАЗВИТИЯ ПАЛОМНИЧЕСКОГО ТУРИЗМА.....	687
Навруз-Зода Бахтиёр Негматович, Мусаев Маликжон Кароматович	

TRANSFORMING UZBEKISTAN THROUGH DIGITALIZATION IN A GLOBALIZED WORLD..... 694
Narzullaeva Umidakhon Nodir qizi

MUNDARIJA SOÐERJANIE CONTENTS

TRANSFORMING UZBEKISTAN THROUGH DIGITALIZATION IN A GLOBALIZED WORLD

Narzullaeva Umidakhon Nodir qizi

Tashkent State University of Economics

PhD, Senior teacher

Email: umidahonnarzullaeva@gmail.com

Abstract. This article presents an in-depth and systematic analysis of digital transformation processes in Uzbekistan and their impact on economic growth, public administration efficiency, and social development. The study is based on the analysis of national digitalization policies, including the “Digital Uzbekistan — 2030” strategy, presidential decrees, and international assessments. The level of digital development is evaluated using key statistical indicators such as internet penetration, the contribution of the ICT sector to GDP, and GovTech performance rankings. The article explores the development of digital infrastructure, the role of human capital, and the formation of an innovation ecosystem. At the same time, it identifies existing challenges, including shortages of qualified specialists, regional disparities in infrastructure, and barriers to integration into the global digital economy. Based on the findings, scientifically grounded conclusions and practical recommendations are proposed to enhance the effectiveness of digital transformation.

Key words: digitalization, sustainable tourism, digital Uzbekistan, AI, igital Governance, ICT Development, GovTech Index, Digital Public Services, Smart Government, Human Capital, Innovation Ecosystem, Data-Driven Policy, Digital Inclusion, Economic Modernization.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada O‘zbekistonda raqamli transformatsiya jarayonlari, uning iqtisodiy o‘shish, davlat boshqaruvi samaradorligi hamda ijtimoiy rivojlanishga ta‘siri kompleks va tizimli tarzda tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqotda mamlakatda amalga oshirilayotgan raqamlashtirish siyosati, xususan, “Raqamli O‘zbekiston — 2030” strategiyasi, Prezident farmonlari hamda xalqaro tashkilotlar tomonidan berilgan baholashlar asosida raqamli rivojlanish darajasi baholangan. Shuningdek, internet qamrovi, AKT sektorining yalpi ichki mahsulotdagi ulushi, GovTech ko‘rsatkichlari kabi statistik ma‘lumotlar orqali mavjud natijalar tahlil qilingan. Maqolada raqamli infratuzilma rivoji, inson kapitalining ahamiyati, innovatsion ekotizimni shakllantirish jarayonlari bilan bir qatorda, malakali kadrlar yetishmovchiligi, hududlararo infratuzilma tafovutlari va global raqamli iqtisodiyotga integratsiyalashuvdagi muammolar ham yoritilgan. Tadqiqot natijasida raqamli transformatsiyaning samaradorligini oshirish bo‘yicha ilmiy asoslangan xulosalar va amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: raqamlashtirish, barqaror turizm, raqamli O‘zbekiston, sun‘iy intellekt, raqamli boshqaruv, AKTni rivojlantirish, GovTech indeksi, raqamli davlat xizmatlari, aqlli hukumat, inson kapitali, innovatsion ekotizim, ma‘lumotlarga asoslangan siyosat, raqamli inklyuziya, iqtisodiy modernizatsiya.

Аннотация. В данной статье проводится углубленный и системный анализ процессов цифровой трансформации в Узбекистане, а также их влияния на экономический рост, эффективность государственного управления и социальное развитие. Исследование основано на анализе государственной политики цифровизации, включая стратегию «Цифровой Узбекистан — 2030», президентские указы и международные оценки. Уровень цифрового развития страны оценивается с использованием статистических показателей, таких как уровень проникновения интернета, вклад ИКТ сектора в ВВП и показатели GovTech. В статье рассматриваются вопросы развития цифровой инфраструктуры, роли человеческого капитала и формирования инновационной экосистемы. Наряду с этим выявляются существующие проблемы, включая дефицит квалифицированных кадров, региональные диспропорции инфраструктуры и ограничения интеграции в глобальную цифровую экономику. По результатам исследования сформулированы научно обоснованные выводы и практические рекомендации по повышению эффективности цифровой трансформации.

Ключевые слова: цифровизация, устойчивый туризм, цифровой Узбекистан, ИИ, цифровое управление, развитие ИКТ, Индекс GovTech, цифровые государственные услуги, умное правительство, человеческий капитал, инновационная экосистема, политика, основанная на данных, цифровая интеграция, экономическая модернизация.

INTRODUCTION

In the 21st century, digitalization has emerged as a defining force of economic growth, governance reform, and societal progress. Countries around the world are rapidly adopting digital technologies — from artificial intelligence and e-government platforms to data-driven public services — to enhance efficiency and competitiveness. Uzbekistan, a key country in Central Asia, has taken strategic steps toward digital transformation under the leadership of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, aligning national priorities with global trends. This article explores Uzbekistan's digitalization journey, based on recent presidential decrees, national strategies, and international evaluations, while situating it within broader global digital transformation experiences.

Recent statistical data confirms the accelerating pace of digital transformation globally and in Uzbekistan. According to DataReportal (2024), Uzbekistan had 29.5 million internet users, representing 83.3% of the population¹, while mobile connections exceeded 95% penetration². The ICT sector accounted for 2.7% of GDP in 2024, with IT service exports reaching \$344 million³. Furthermore, Uzbekistan ranked 9th globally in the World Bank's GovTech Maturity Index in 2025, entering the "high maturity" group alongside advanced digital economies⁴.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Digitalization refers to the use of digital technologies to transform traditional systems, processes, and interactions across sectors. It extends beyond simple computerization: digitalization reshapes economic models, public services, and social engagement by leveraging data, connectivity, and automation. According to international frameworks, digitalization includes: integration of digital tools into government services, adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) in public and private sectors, expansion of digital skills in the workforce and development of digital infrastructure, such as broadband and cloud services. G. Vial argued that digital transformation is a process that aims to improve an entity by triggering significant changes to its properties through combinations of information, computing, communication, and connectivity technologies⁵. This widely cited definition emphasizes that digital transformation is not just about technology, but about fundamental changes in systems, processes, and organizational structures. Globally, digitalization is recognized as a driver of productivity and innovation. The World Bank's GovTech Maturity Index 2025 places emphasis on the ability of governments to integrate digital solutions in public administration, indicating that digital maturity correlates strongly with governance quality⁶.

As M.Abdurashidova and Sh.Nematov say digital technologies play a significant role in enhancing the quality of higher education, promoting a dynamic learning environment and improved student engagement⁷. This confirms that digitalization in Uzbekistan affects not only infrastructure but also the quality of education, increasing student engagement and making learning more adaptive. It aligns well with the national strategy for digital modernization of education.

A foundational milestone in Uzbekistan's digital transformation is the presidential decree approving the "Digital Uzbekistan — 2030" strategy⁸. This decree outlines long-term goals for digital governance, economic modernization, and ICT development. Its key objectives include: implementation of e-government services and digital public administration, expansion of IT parks and digital hubs across regions, development of domestic digital products and software as well as advancement of digital skills through education and training programs. This strategy lays the groundwork for a national digital ecosystem that fosters innovation, transparency, and inclusivity. It signals Uzbekistan's commitment to joining the ranks of digitally advanced nations by 2030.

In addition to the 2030 strategy, another presidential decree further emphasizes digital transformation priorities. It highlights transition toward a "digital government" model with fully digitized public services, launch of regional digital programs to improve governance at local levels and strengthening digital skills for citizens, including women, youth, and workers across sectors. These legislative decisions reflect a structured, high-level approach to national digital transformation⁹.

1 [Digital 2024: Uzbekistan — DataReportal — Global Digital Insights](#), 2024

2 [Digital 2024: Uzbekistan — DataReportal — Global Digital Insights](#), 2024

3 <https://invest.gov.uz/en/investment-guide/technology>, 2024

4 Uzbekistan Enters Global Top 10 in World Bank GovTech Index, 2025

[Uzbekistan Enters Global Top 10 in World Bank GovTech Index — UzDaily.uz](#)

5 Gregory Vial, Journal of Strategic Information Systems, 2019. sciencedirect.com

6 World Bank. (2025). GovTech Maturity Index Update

7 Marina Abdurashidova, Sherzod Nematov et al., The impact of innovation and digitalization on the quality of higher education: A study of selected universities in Uzbekistan (Journal of Intelligent Systems, 2023). researchgate.net

8 [DP-6079-coh 05.10.2020. On approval of the Strategy "Digital Uzbekistan-2030" and measures for its effective implementation](#)

9 Presidential decree-76, May, 2023

S. Gulyamov noticed that The Republic of Uzbekistan made the digitalization and development of information-communication technologies priority yet in early 2000s... digital infrastructure and e-government have achieved visible results in a relatively short period of time¹⁰. This illustrates that Uzbekistan's digitalization has been a long-term strategic effort. Early investments in infrastructure and e-government have provided tangible results, supporting the country's rapid digital growth.

The rapid rise of Uzbekistan in global digital rankings illustrates measurable outcomes of reform. Between 2020 and 2025, the country improved its GovTech ranking from 80th to 9th place, with its index score increasing from 0.617 to 0.958¹¹. This reflects significant progress in digital public services, citizen engagement platforms, and institutional digital capacity.

According to B. Usmonov it is simply impossible not to use digital in order to keep up with further processes of informatization and digitalization in education¹². This highlights the necessity of adopting digital technologies in Uzbek universities to stay aligned with global education trends. It supports national strategies like "Digital Uzbekistan" for higher education.

Academic research highlights that despite rapid growth, digital transformation in emerging economies offers significant potential for structural advancement. A study published in *Labor Economics and Human Capital* (2024) emphasizes that Uzbekistan's ICT sector development is driven by the ongoing growth of qualified specialists, continuous improvement of infrastructure, and expanding opportunities for integration into global markets¹³. These findings suggest that sustainable digitalization requires not only policy reforms but also long-term investment in human capital and innovation ecosystems.

Realizing digital transformation requires institutional capacity. In Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Digital Technologies plays a central role. Created through presidential reform efforts, this ministry is responsible for coordinating digital governance initiatives, supporting innovation ecosystems, and overseeing public IT integration. Alongside the ministry, technical agencies such as UZINFOCOM help implement core digital infrastructure, for instance, UZINFOCOM manages state information systems, the national domain, and digital public services portals like MyGov, it also develops educational and cybersecurity projects, including cloud services and digital platforms for schools. Together, these institutions anchor Uzbekistan's digital transformation with technological, administrative, and regulatory capacities. Jr. Singun noted that there are multiple barriers hindering the implementation of Digital Transformation (DT) in Higher Education Institutions which must be navigated successfully¹⁴.

Uzbekistan has made demonstrable progress in digitizing public services. National platforms now provide online access to many government procedures, reducing bureaucratic barriers and expanding convenience for citizens. Recent reports highlight the country's placement in the A group of the GovTech Maturity Index 2025, which indicates high maturity in digital public administration relative to 197 countries worldwide. Participation in international forums on artificial intelligence, such as events where President Mirziyoyev engaged with startups and youth innovators, reflects a national emphasis on future technologies and innovation ecosystems. Another important development — based on presidential guidance — is the digital reform of the courts. Introducing AI tools to court systems and digitizing proceedings can enhance case management, transparency, and access to justice. The financial sector in Uzbekistan has witnessed significant digital transformation. Remote banking services and data-driven banking infrastructure have reshaped financial interactions, with an increased focus on user experience and ecosystem integration.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative and analytical research methodology to examine the process of digital transformation in Uzbekistan within a global context. The research is based on the analysis of secondary data sources, including official presidential decrees of the Republic of Uzbekistan, national development strategies such as "Digital Uzbekistan – 2030", and reports from international organizations such as the World Bank, OECD, and the United Nations. In addition, the study incorporates comparative analysis to evaluate Uzbekistan's digital progress relative to global trends. Statistical data from 2024–2025, including indicators of internet penetration, ICT contribution to GDP, and GovTech rankings, are used to assess the effectiveness of digital reforms. Academic literature from Google Scholar and ResearchGate platforms is also reviewed to

10 Saidasror Gulyamov et al., Experience of development of digital technologies in Uzbekistan (E3S Web of Conferences, 2023). researchgate.net

11 Uzbekistan Enters Global Top 10 in World Bank GovTech Index, 2025
[Uzbekistan Enters Global Top 10 in World Bank GovTech Index — UzDaily.uz](https://uzdaily.uz/news/uzbekistan-enters-global-top-10-in-world-bank-govtech-index-2025)

12 Usmonov Botir, Higher Education in Uzbekistan: Transition to Digital Learning (Education Journal, 2024). researchgate.net

13 DEVELOPMENT STATUS OF THE INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES SECTOR OF UZBEKISTAN: ANALYSIS FOR 2017-2024, Abdullayev Abdulla Fayzulla ugli

14 Amando Jr. Singun, Discover Education, 2025.

provide theoretical support and identify common challenges in digital transformation processes. The combination of policy analysis, statistical evaluation, and comparative approach allows for a comprehensive understanding of both the achievements and limitations of digitalization in Uzbekistan.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

As Li Shin highlighted that digital transformation research has moved into a rapid growth stage and covers topics such as AI, big data, blockchain, cloud computing, security and risk management¹⁵. This meta-analysis shows that digitalization is a global scientific topic covering multiple technologies. It reinforces the need for Uzbekistan to integrate AI, big data, and other innovations into its national strategy. The findings of this study demonstrate that Uzbekistan has achieved significant progress in digital transformation over the past five years. The implementation of national strategies and presidential decrees has resulted in the rapid expansion of e-government services, increased accessibility of digital platforms, and improved public service delivery. Statistical evidence indicates a steady increase in internet penetration, reaching over 83% of the population in 2024, along with a high level of mobile connectivity exceeding 95%¹⁶. The ICT sector has also shown positive growth, contributing approximately 2.7% to national GDP¹⁷. One of the most notable achievements is Uzbekistan's advancement in the World Bank GovTech Maturity Index, where it rose to 9th place globally by 2025.

Global authorities such as the World Bank, OECD, and region-specific development banks stress that digitalization is not simply technological adoption — it is a transformation of governance, economy, and social structures. In global indices, investments in ICT, data governance, AI, and broadband connectivity are strongly correlated with economic resilience and competitiveness. For instance, digital maturity assessments, such as the GovTech Index, emphasize digital legal frameworks, high-quality data systems, citizen-centric service models, inclusive access to broadband and digital skills education. These international perspectives align with Uzbekistan's strategic priorities and highlight the country's potential to accelerate development through digitalization.

Recent academic research also demonstrates that digital competitiveness depends on a combination of ICT investment, foreign direct investment, and institutional quality. According to a 2025 study on digital trade competitiveness, countries that simultaneously invest in broadband infrastructure and innovation ecosystems can increase their competitiveness by up to 50–60% in medium-term scenarios¹⁸. This highlights the importance of integrated digital strategies rather than isolated reforms.

Looking ahead, Uzbekistan's digital economy is expected to grow significantly by 2030. Based on current trends, several projections can be identified: Internet penetration is expected to approach near-universal levels (over 90%), driven by mobile expansion and infrastructure investments. The ICT sector's contribution to GDP may double, reaching 5–6% as digital services and exports expand. What is more, Uzbekistan is likely to strengthen its position in global digital rankings, potentially entering the top 5 in GovTech development if reforms continue. Artificial intelligence and data-driven governance will become key pillars of public administration.

However, achieving these outcomes will depend on addressing cybersecurity risks, improving digital literacy, and ensuring inclusive access to technology across rural areas.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Uzbekistan's journey toward digital transformation is rooted in strategic presidential policies, institutional reforms, and global engagement. The “Digital Uzbekistan — 2030” strategy, supported by additional decrees and implementation frameworks, demonstrates a comprehensive vision for technological governance, economic modernization, and human capital development. While challenges — such as digital skills gaps and infrastructure disparities — remain, Uzbekistan's recent achievements in public sector digitalization and innovation ecosystems position it as a leading example of digital transformation in Central Asia. As countries worldwide continue to adapt to the Fourth Industrial Revolution, Uzbekistan's efforts reflect both national ambition and alignment with global digital development trajectories.

List of used literature:

1. Rasulova, Nigora. “SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL BASIS OF GREENTOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN.” SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL JOURNAL “SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE” 23, no. 3 (2024): 70-71.

15 Lin Shi et al., Digital Transformation: A Bibliometric Analysis (ResearchGate, 2025).

16 Key findings of ITU's “Measuring Digital Development: Facts and Figures 2024” report

17 Uzbekistan Expands ICT Sector Amidst Rising Global Demand, N. Umarova, 2025

18 Forecasting ICT-Driven Trade Competitiveness 2024-2028: A Cluster and Scenario Analysis, Cornell University, Aravantinos, E, 2025

- Rasulova, N. Yashil Mehmonxonalarda Strategik Tahlil Metodologiyasi. *Green Economy and Development*, 3(6), 665855.
- Рахимова, Д. М. «МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ОПЫТ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИМ ТУРИЗМОМ.» Архив научных исследований 2.1 (2022).
- Raximova, Dilfuza. "O 'zbekistonda Smart-turizmni Rivojlantirish Choralari." *Green Economy and Development* 1.10 (2023): 662814.
- Narzullayeva, Umidakhon. "DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION AND THE NEW APPROACHES IN TOURISM." *ZAMONAVIY TA'LIMDA FAN VA INNOVATSION TADQIQOTLAR* 2.12 (2024): 27-32.
- Narzullaeva, Umidakhon. "IMPORTANCE OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN THE TRAVEL INDUSTRY." Универсальная индексная библиотека инновационных исследований в современном мире: теория и практика 3.3 (2024): 83-86.
- Махзуна, Х. Г. «Strategy for Increasing the Attractiveness of National Tourism Products (In A Basis Of Craftsmanship)[Стратегия повышения привлекательности национальных туристических продуктов (на основе ремесленничества)].» *Молодой специалист* 2.14 (2023): 24-27.
- Gulamjanovna, M. K. "Current Issues Of Tourism Potential Of Uzbekistan And Its Development." *Scientific Aspects And Trends In The Field Of Scientific Research* 1.10 (2023): 342-346.
- Khushnazarova, Makhzuna, et al. "Cognitive Radio Network Applications in Mountain Tourism: A Case Study of Uzbekistan's Mountainous Regions." *Proceedings of the 8th International Conference on Future Networks & Distributed Systems*. 2024.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2026. № 4

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin.
Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>
